

Mathematical formulation of sensible heat transfer in the spatially heterogeneous skin-clothing-environment system

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Introduction

The heat and mass transfer from the human body to the environment is of interest for many scientific fields such as clothing research, indoor climate and automotive environment (car upholstery). Thermal manikins have been frequently used to analyse the heat and mass transfer from the human body. These experimental methods are often very time-consuming. The theoretical clothing models provide more detailed spatial and temporal data for a better understanding of heat transfer mechanisms in the air and the material layer of clothing. However, there are no reliable clothing models that consider spatial heterogeneity and natural convection in air layers of clothing. The aim of this paper is to present a theoretical model that considers the spatial heterogeneity of air layers and natural convection. The model was extensively validated using several cases with increasing level of geometrical complexity addressing realistic and typical clothing scenarios.

Methods

The presented theoretical clothing model is based on the assumption of one-dimensional and steady-state system with constant fabric properties[1]. The temperature difference between skin and fabric along with gravitational force induce the natural convection in an enclosed air layer. The shape of the enclosed air layer is approximated as a rectangular cavity with a wide range of aspect ratio (ratio of height to width). A model for predicting the natural convective heat transfer is obtained by various non-dimensional numbers, such as Nusselt, Rayleigh and Grashof number[1].

Table 1 Experimental conditions, fabric properties

	R_{ct} (W/m^2)	v_a (m/s)	T_{sk} (°C)	T_a (°C)	Air gap (mm)	fcl (-)	Residual (%)
Case 1	0.012	0.2	35	20	50	1.33	1.2
Case 2	0.012	0.2	35	20	23	1.15	9.3
Case 3	0.012	0.2	35	20	5	1.10	12.4
Case 4	0.012	0.15	34	24	10.1	1.06	0.5
Case 5	0.012	0.15	34	05	42.6	1.28	8.1

Figure 1 Configuration of fold around thermal cylinder[2] and manikin for different experimental cases.

To calculate the heat flux from spatially heterogeneous air layers, air layers can be discretized into small elements. As each element is at a different distance from the skin, temperature distribution and heat transfer could be different at each element. Considering each discretized element as homogeneous, computation of temperature distribution and heat transfer for all the elements and integrating it will give equivalent heat transfer for spatially heterogeneous air layers [1].

To validate the clothing model experimental cases with increasing level of spatial complexity were systematically chosen as shown in Figure 1 and Table 1. The data variability for the experimental measurement was less than 5%.

Results

Figure 2 Validation of theoretical models to the experimental data, and comparison of radiative and convective heat transfer coefficient for different cases,*predominantly conduction

The mathematical clothing model presented in this paper is systematically validated for increasing level of spatial complexity of air layers. The clothing model precisely predicted the heat flux from the thermal cylinder and anatomically shaped thermal manikin as shown in Figure 2. The average error in simulated heat flux was 5.3% (between -12.4% and 9.3%) as compared to average data variability of 2.8%. The clothing model provides detailed insight into fundamentals of heat transfer process; it offers fragmentation of total heat transfer into different heat transfer mechanisms such as radiation, convection and conduction. The detailed analysis of heat transfer in the skin-clothing-environment system can be very useful for optimization purpose in clothing research.

Conclusions

In this paper, a mathematical clothing model for sensible heat transfer is presented, which considers the natural convection and spatial heterogeneity of air layers. The presented model is accurate and reliable for the chosen scenarios, as it is validated against many complex experimental measurements. The clothing model can simulate the heat transfer for an anatomically shaped thermal manikin. Thus, it is applicable for many research fields where analysis of thermal environment around human body is in focus, for e.g. in thermal physiology, automotive and HVAC simulations.

References

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